

Role of Religion and Culture on Female Labor Force Participation: A Panel Data Analysis of Selected Countries

Fouzia Yasmin , Noreen Safdar, Faima Ali, Iqra Ashraf

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 05, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 09, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Female Labor Force Participation, Religion, Religiosity, Culture, PCA Index, Logistic Regression</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6017482</p>	<p><i>Recent research regarding the role of Religion and Culture in female labor force participation has recently gained pace to understand various broader societal and personal level factors. Women's higher participation in the labor force is essential for boosting the global economy and creating a more equitable society. The influence of religion, religiosity, and culture was explored using five waves of the World Values Survey (WVS) ranging from 1989 to 2014, and Panel logistics regression analysis was used for empirical results. In addition, principal component analysis was utilized to create indices for culture, religion, and religiosity. The results showed that religiosity and traditional culture negatively affected the FLFPR, while no conclusive statement could be made about the impact of religion. Results show that religion, religiosity, and culture remain dominant influencers of female employment despite the individual variation. Hence, it is essential to consider the various aspects of their national cultural and dominant religion and develop policies in tandem with these cultural and religious frameworks.</i></p>

Introduction

Female labor force participation (FLFP) is one of the critical drivers of global economic progress as the world economy stands to gain GDP increase from the increased participation of women in the workforce (Alam & Ansari, 2020; Lechman & Kaur, 2015). Moreover, gender equality in labor force participation has been identified as an unequivocal preamble to more comprehensive societal benefit for all participants (Besamusca, Tijdens, Keune, & Steinmetz, 2015). However, while the last few decades have seen a rise in FLFP for several countries, a considerable variation in the FLFP rate remains among the various countries and regions. Hence, understanding the determinants of these differences among regions is a fundamental problem in global economics.

(Kuiper & Barker, 2006; Tzannatos, 1999) Argued that while traditional economic factors can explain this chasm, non-economic factors such as cultural traditions, norms, and religion are the most significant factors determining FLFP levels in a country or region. For example, the role of women in society usually determines the participation rate of women in society. This role is usually determined by the existing structure of the prevalent religious community and the underlying text (Klingorova & Havlíček, 2015). Sharabi (2011) has also pointed to the religious traditions, particularly those related to Islam, that define women's conservative role, predominantly restraining their participation in the broader workforce. On the other hand, some researchers believe that the economic situation overrides religious traditions in determining FLFP. For example, (Zelekha, Avnimelech, & Sharabi, 2014) has argued that high-income levels and traditional Islamic views have driven women away from the workforce in oil-rich Muslim countries (H'madoun, 2010a).

It is important to note that in any study carried out to understand the role of religion in a society, a firm reference has to be made to the society's broader culture as religion cannot be separated from the culture of a society (Sharabi, Shdema, & Abboud-Armaly, 2020; Womick, Woody, & King, 2021). Moreover, religion and culture have a strong relationship as they continue to influence each other over time and continue to weave the social fabric that defines any society (Sinclair, 1986; Taj & Sinclair, 2020). Hence, this study will make necessary reference to cultural and religious aspects as well.

2. Literature review

Ho (2011) analyzed the effect of culture on female labor participation. This study used the International Social Survey Program (ISSP) data set in conjunction with Hofstede's five-dimension cultural model (Gu, Tan, Amin, Mostafiz, & Yeoh, 2021) and Globe's eight-dimension cultural model as a proxy for culture. This study built an indicator variable for labor force participation (LFP) equal to one of the female respondents was currently employed and zero if otherwise as the dependent variable. This study used independent variables completion of higher education, marital status, household size and family income, and two alternative proxies for culture. The study also included GDP, HDI, and TUD (Trade Union Density). The study firstly estimated the probit model and then estimated a model that substituted the country dummy variables with a cultural proxy separately

for the Hofstede and the Globe Measures. Globe culture like gender egalitarianism and uncertainty avoidance positively associated with the female labor force, and assertiveness was negatively associated with the female labor force. The study also found that the Globe culture study rather than the Hofstede study was a better proxy for culture.

(Fernández, 2013) analyzed the evolution of female labor force participation over a century due to culture change and examined the role of variations in culture in creating the histrionic growth in married female labor force participation over the last century. This study examined that these beliefs had endogenously through a process of learning across generations. Females were supposed to learn regarding the payouts of working in the market in the long run by detecting private and public indicators. It examined that this process produced the S-shaped diagram for women labor force participation by using data. The study analyzed the cross-sectional model and inferences across generations. It analyzed that the model determined a new role for variations in wages through their impact on learning across generations, and the study analyzed that this adjustment highlighted the role of changes in wages was numerically significant in several years.

Diwan and Vartanova (2017) analyzed the effect of patriarchal culture on the participation of women in the labor force. The study used the World Value Survey (WVS) data of the last two waves, 2005 and 2013, of 80 countries. This study treated female labor participation (FLP) as the dependent variable. It was a dummy dependent binary variable. This study used a linear probability model (LPM) and checked the robustness of the result with the Probit model. This study included the education, age, marital status, number of children, controlled for religion variable by using Christian, Muslim, Other, or none and measured religiosity by using the binary variable "if religious faith was chosen as the desired quality for children" and this study finally used a measure of relative household income at the individual level. But at the level of the country, this study controlled for a log of GDP per capita, size of agriculture, manufacturing, government expenditures, as a share in GDP, share of civil servants in total labor by using the data of WVS and regions by geographical location, and by main religions. This study also found that measures of patriarchal culture were associated with female labor force participation (FLFP) and women's levels of education, including personal norms and values and customs of the country regarding patriarchy, describe a large extent of regional changes in FLFP detected around the world. This study argued that FLFP could be raised through the effect of better-quality education on the household's income and its effect on patriarchal values and on negotiating the position of women. So, this study mentioned these three effects of education to enhance the female labor participation rate.

Diwan and Vartanova (2017) This study used the data of India Human Development Survey Data (IHDS) of 2004-05. This study used a binary dummy dependent variable that took a value of one if the individual was working more than 240 hours in a year and 0 otherwise to show workforce participation and struggle in the labor market. In addition, the study used the age of the respondent, age, education, household assets, sex, caste, and household's total income as independent variables. Estimation was done by using the Probit model. This study found that females belonging to stronger patriarchal backgrounds would do worse in the labor market as compared to those females who were from liberal families and, such impact of family culture wouldn't be detected for the men. But the study found some differences in the observed results depending on the site (rural/urban) of work and nature of the job.

Many pieces of evidence make contributions to the area of FLFP. First, prior studies have chosen to analyze specific regions (Fukuda-Parr, Heintz, & Seguino, 2013; Seguino, 2011) or even a single country (Alam & Ansari, 2020), while on the other hand (H'madoun, 2010b; Tausch & Heshmati, 2016) have studied the determinants of FLFP for a broader geographic region. However, they do not include cultural variables in their analysis. Second, many studies have claimed that the strong influence of religion is among the most significant factors that discourage women from either participating in the labor market or pursuing a career in societies present in Asian, Eastern African, and Middle Eastern regions (Maton, Dodgen, Sto. Domingo, & Larson, 2005; Tausch & Heshmati, 2016). The importance of religion, religiosity, and culture to FLFP established here helps ease this dilemma for economic policymakers in women's employment. Third, studies allow them to chalk up the frameworks which comply with more essential factors only.

Reimer (1995) identified how cultural differences among people belonging to different ethnicities impacted the employment prospect of married women. It was determined that the underlying culture defines an ideal wife's role, which ultimately impacted entering the workforce. A cross-national study (Clark, 1985) found a similar relationship between culture and FLFP. Mahony (1995) discussed at length how families enter in a sort of bargaining and contest for roles of either being a breadwinner or child-bearer, and the result of this bargaining influences women's decision to take a job or stay at home. Finally, Amin, Diamond, Naved, and Newby (1998) studied the case of underdeveloped countries where economic difficulties push women to enter the labor market despite conflicting with the country's culture.

(Glass & Nath, 2006) analyzed the impact of religious traditionalism on women's behavior to join the labor force, get married, or add a new child to their family. This study used the data of the National Survey (1988 – 1993) of Families and Households (N = 3,494). This study was used to model how variations in women's labor

supply, jobs, and wages were treated as a function of traditional denominational membership, and conventional belief of religion and other economic and demographic variables were treated as constant. As Whites were concerned, conventional denominations declined women's labor supply due to a marriage or a marital birth, while conventional spiritual beliefs had more significant impacts on the choice of occupation and wages. Conversely, as Blacks were concerned, conventional religious affiliation enlarged women's labor supply due to marital births, but both denomination and belief did not affect occupation and wage growth. Similarly, the findings of this study expressed the significance of the ideology of religion for the understanding of persistent gender inequality in the labor market.

Nnoromele (2017) examined the effects of religion and patriarchal norms on female labor force participation. This study proposed an empirical study assessing the effect of religion, religiosity, and patriarchal norms on the behavior of females to join the labor force across 40 countries. The study used the micro-level data from the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP) 2012: "Family and Changing Gender Roles IV and macro-level data from World Bank Group's Women, Business, and the Law 2012 database. The study included women aged 15-64 years. This study modeled female labor participation as a dummy dependent variable of religion, religiosity, patriarchal norms and values, legal discrimination, and many demographic variables. This study estimated the probit regression to examine the impact of religion, religiosity, and patriarchal norms on female labor participation. This investigation supported the supposition that the more religious women and had conventional mentality too probably less participated in paid employment. But this study which investigated ten different religions, found that the particular religion of a female that she was being practiced, apart from the cultural religions (Judaism and Hinduism), didn't affect the female participation in the labor force when the study controlled for national and environmental cultural factors. This analysis recommended that all the things like institutions of a country, socio and political context, and geographic, cultural heritage have much worth and value in the way that religiosity was clearly shown in women's participation in the labor force and its effects the economic growth.

Spierings and Smits (2007) analyzed Women's participation in the labor market of Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, Syria & Tunisia. The study used representative data covering over 50,000 women and over 65 districts by including five MENA countries (Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, Syria, and Tunisia). This study estimated the multilevel logit model. This study claimed that desires, opportunities, and attitudes played a vital role at different levels in the decision of females to join the formal labor market or restrict them to join the labor market. Anyhow, tertiary education looks the most significant aspect for increasing women's formal labor market participation (LMP). At the macrolevel, an attitudinal factor was significantly associated with the dependent variable women's formal labor market participation (LMP). Many macro-level factors were probably significant, but their impact looks to be more practical through micro-level features.

Vega Arias (2020) studied the interplay between FLFP, religious beliefs, and the relocation of low-skilled female workers. The study explored that liberation combined with strong religious beliefs have a crucial strength and power to women as they face employment challenges. Seguino (2011) studied the link between an individual's level of religiosity and the typical attitude they have towards (in)equality among genders. The study has used data from World Values Survey for almost 300,000 individual respondents for five distinct waves. It was concluded that religion plays an indirect or relatively hidden role in female employment. Kus (2011) discussed religion's role in determining females' participation in the labor force. Islam and Catholicism were the primal examined religion of this research. Researchers concluded that religion plays a vital role in determining females' participation in the labor force within Catholic and Islamic economies. Finally, (Pastore & Tenaglia, 2013) discussed the influence of religion on women's labor supply for 47 European countries using data from the European Values Study (EVS). Analysis based on EVS concluded that religion substantially impacts the women labor force according to their country's culture.

Spierings (2014) explores the determining for the role of Islam in non-farm paid employment of women who work in provinces from Indonesian and Nigerian. Multilevel multinomial logit models reflected that Islam played a significant role in determining non-farm paid employment for women.

Yonay, Yaish, and Kraus (2015) discussed the heterogeneity in culture and religion. Therefore, researchers considered the effect of Christian on Muslim neighbor's labor force participation for the case study of Israel's economy. Overall findings were that female participation was significantly influenced by social interaction.

Abdelhadi (2019) studied panel data for employment of Muslim women in the USA and explored its link to religiosity. It was determined that the majority of religiosity variables have no significant role in determining employment levels. Other factors such as level of education, ethnic background, and motherhood were relatively strong in predicting FLFP for Muslim women in the United States.

3. Data and Methodology

3.1 Source of Data

This research adopts a quantitative data approach to measure the influence of religion on females' labor force participation. For estimation, the researcher utilizes Panel data throughout 1990-2014. Data were collected from

the different waves of the world value survey, i.e., wave 2 (1990-1994), wave 3 (1995-1998), wave 4 (1999-2004), wave 5 (2004-2009), and wave 6 (2010-2014). Different variables from the families (groups) of religion, religiosity, culture, and control variables have been taken for analysis. The control variables used here include age, gender, race/ethnicity, income levels, and marital status.

3.2 Model specification

The following models describe the use of verifiable evidence to arrive at research outcomes of three different models:

The analysis was done by using the below three models:

a) Association between religion and FLFP

$$(FLFP) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 AGE_{ti} + \alpha_2 AGEDU_{ti} + \alpha_3 SCLAS_{ti} + \alpha_4 CHLD_{ti} + \alpha_5 TRST_{ti} + \alpha_6 ATAS_{ti} + \alpha_7 RLGIti + \varepsilon$$

b) Association between culture and FLFP

$$(FLFP) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 AGE_{ti} + \alpha_2 AGEDU_{ti} + \alpha_3 SCLAS_{ti} + \alpha_4 CHLD_{ti} + \alpha_5 TRST_{ti} + \alpha_6 ATAS_{ti} + \alpha_7 BCHO_{ti} + \alpha_8 CULT_{ti} + \alpha_9 RELGIti + \varepsilon$$

c) Association between religiosity and FLFP

$$(FLFP) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 AGE_{ti} + \alpha_2 AGEDU_{ti} + \alpha_3 SCLAS_{ti} + \alpha_4 CHLD_{ti} + \alpha_5 TRST_{ti} + \alpha_6 ATAS_{ti} + \alpha_7 RELOG_{ti} + \alpha_8 CULT_{ti} + \alpha_9 RELGIti + \varepsilon$$

d) Association between religion, religiosity, culture, and FLFP

$$(FLFP) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 AGE_{ti} + \alpha_2 AGEDU_{ti} + \alpha_3 SCLAS_{ti} + \alpha_4 CHLD_{ti} + \alpha_5 TRST_{ti} + \alpha_6 ATAS_{ti} + \alpha_7 RELOG_{ti} + \alpha_8 CULT_{ti} + \alpha_9 RELGIti + \varepsilon$$

Correlation analysis

Correlation analysis

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.
EMPL	0.886824	0.3170753
EMPLSTS	4.021959	1.310323
FRDM	17.11824	26.93112
AGE	36.65709	14.91711
AGEDU	16.97635	6.063074
MRTS	1.652027	0.7104699
SCLAS	2.347973	1.196666
CHLD	1.636824	2.087315
TRST	1.777027	.4842137
RLGI	5.025338	.3553315
RELOG	1.135135	.4990502
CULT	.3509617	.1416006
ATAS	1.478041	.49994
BCHO	.2274883	.2237022

Source: Author's estimation using STATA 14

Table 1 demonstrates the correlation coefficients between variables, and the value shows the association among the variables.

Pooled Logit regression Results

Table 2: Association between Religion, religiosity, and, FLFP

Variables	Coefficient	p-value	dy/dx	p-value
AGE	-.0006429	0.963	-.0000524	0.963
AGEDU	.0027609	0.929	.1301319	0.001
MRTS	-.2928193	0.158	-.0238853	0.153
SCLAS	-.2784551	0.011	-.0227136	0.010
CHLD	.4250719	0.000	.0346732	0.000
TRST	-.2014883	0.485	-.0164354	0.484
ATAS	-.5093406	0.061	-.041547	0.059
RLGI	.4225421	0.000	-.0339821	0.142
CONS	6.03527	0.000		

Source: Author's estimation using STATA 14

The first model of the research enhanced the impact of religion (Religion index) on the female labor force participation rate. This model attempts to understand the combined impact of other control variables combined

with religion. The estimated coefficient shows that the marginal effect has the signs according to the theory. They are interpreted as AGE has negative it the female labor supply the marginal impact is equaled to -.0000524

That is not significant. AGEDU has a positive impact it the female labor supply. The marginal impact is equal to .1301319. MRTS has negative it the female labor supply the marginal impact significant and equals to -.0238853. Social class has a negative marginal impact concerning the base category that is equal to -.0227136. The number of children positively impacts the paid work decision. The Marginal impact is 0.0346732.

Similarly, the TRST has -.0164354, ATAS has -.041547, RLGI, the most crucial variable, has a negative -.0339821 marginal impact sign. Coefficients were negative for religion. Results indicate that higher education, higher income levels, and identifying oneself with religion were positively correlated with FLFP. Marital status and age were negatively correlated, but the results were not significant. Marginal analysis shows that the marital status led to the highest incremental decline in FLFP. Education was found to be weakly correlated, and education level has a minimal relationship with FLFP. This result is not in line with the literature and may be due to various reasons, such as outliers in our dataset or inefficient metrics.

Table3: Association between culture and FLFP

Variables	Coefficient	p-value	dy/dx	p-value
AGE	-.004281	0.772	-.0002483	0.773
AGEDU	.4396901	0.000	.7955904	0.000
MRTS	-.3137743	0.157	-.0182	0.155
SCLAS	-.2302799	0.061	-.0133571	0.064
CHLD	.5949749	0.000	.0345107	0.000
TRST	-.4276488	0.179	-.0248052	0.180
ATAS	-.4568475	0.127	-.0264988	0.133
CULT	5.563338	0.000	.3226936	0.000
BCHO	-.6764932	0.367	-.039239	0.370
CONS	2.442753	0.068		

Source: Author's estimations using STATA14

This model has estimated the impact of culture on female labor force participation. At the same time, control variables were the same as in model 1. The results show that culture has a positive coefficient representing a negative link between more traditional beliefs and the probability of an individual being employed. The low margin rate for culture shows that incremental differences among various participants were low. The result is significant, given a bit of p-value. It is important to note that the impact of control variables was consistent with the previous model as no behavior within control does not change even in the absence of religion. Thus, the positive coefficient for culture is consistent with the literature. Research work conducted by (Atasoy, 2017) also showed that traditionalism is linked to lower FLFP. Traditional culture assigns the role of child-bearer and homemaker to women, and this strict gender role assignment leads to a lower participation rate (Uür, 2018).

Furthermore, traditional cultures tend to discourage women from taking employment. It implies that women who tend to hold a predominantly traditional view of the world or belong to a more traditional culture are less likely to participate in labor. This also shows that people tend to behave as per their cultural values. Hence, any effort to increase FLFP needs to consider the existing cultural dimension, and the policy-making needs to be in sync with these underlying characteristics.

Table4: Association between religiosity and FLFP

Variables	Coefficient	p-value	dy/dx	p-value
AGE	0.0005581	0.968	0.000045	0.968
AGEDU	-0.4357141	0.043	0.663422	0.085
MRTS	-0.2852301	0.169	-0.023386	0.164
SCLAS	-0.2701096	0.014	-0.022146	0.013
CHLD	0.4175768	0.000	0.034237	0.000
TRST	-0.2092033	0.468	-0.017153	0.467
ATAS	-0.5266735	0.051	-0.043183	0.050
RELOGS	3.635836	0.004	0.2772551	0.011
CONS	0.2106901	0.491		

The results for both religion and culture were highly significant evident from their lowest p values of marginal effects. The positive coefficient of religiosity is in line with the literature. For example, (Dollar & Gatti, 1999) have established that lower-income groups are more likely to seek employment opportunities. Similarly, (Abazi & Atanasovska, 2016) found a negative correlation between income and FLFP. The result

could be due to several factors, including reverse causality or multicollinearity between income level and FLFP or the presence of auto-correlation in the income function itself. The high-income level may correspond to better education opportunities, which may have increased the employability of the respondents. However, this relationship was not measured, and it is a gap that future research work can fill. The religiosity directly correlates with the existing literature (Kortt, Dollery, & Grant, 2013). Prior research has described insistence associated with the majority religion relates to higher chances of finding employment for women and leads to higher FLFP.

Table 4: Association between religion, religiosity, culture, and FLFP

Variables	Coefficient	p-value	dy/dx	p-value
AGE	-0.0058026	0.697	-.0003395	-.0003
AGEDU	0.1301319	0.001	.0001052	0.958
MRTS	-0.314324	0.154	-.0183925	0.153
SCLAS	-0.239249	0.052	-.0139995	0.054
CHLD	0.586173	0.000	.0342997	0.000
TRST	-0.4064751	0.177	-.0237847	0.183
ATAS	-0.514127	0.157	-0.030083	0.162
RELOGS	0.1257902	0.684	0.007360	0.684
RELGI	-0.7745118	0.303	-0.174333	0.153
CULT	4.1097658	0.000	0.225551	0.000
CONS	4.605805	0.049		

Source: Author's estimation using STATA14

The final model determines the combined influence of religion, religiosity, and culture and the same control variables as previous models. The changed direction of religion requires further analysis due to the interplay between culture and religion. Hence, the final model results show that we cannot conclusively say that religion positively or negatively impacts FLFP. Several authors have previously highlighted this dilemma where by inconclusive evidence on the link between Religion and FLFP. The influence of Religion diminishes when a temporal view is adopted. (Abdelhadi, 2017; O'Brien & Abdelhadi, 2020) also found no evidence that Islamization was linked to lower FLFP. Consistent with the previous models, religiosity and traditional culture has a negative coefficient, evidencing their detrimental impact on a woman's employment probability. However, being associated with religion, which is positively affected in the previous model, tends to be negatively correlated and introduces culture in the final model. Control variables continue to be consistent with the prior model.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

Women's higher participation in the global workforce is linked with higher economic growth and GDP gains. Hence, it has been a topic of interest for both policymakers and economics researchers alike. The research work conducted in the area of FLFP has traditionally been around the neoclassical view. More recently, economists have forayed into exploring the link between FLFP and non-economic variables such as religion.

Religion and culture have been identified by many as critical influencers on individual decision-making, and a woman's decision to enter the workforce is no different. However, despite the extensive work done in this area, little attention has been paid to exploring the impact of religion, religiosity, and culture together.

Additionally, very few genuinely global studies exist in the extant literature as most researchers have opted to focus on single countries or geographies. Conclusions stated that the primary motivation for the current study is to fill this void in the literature and explore the interplay between religion, religiosity, culture, and FLFP. The results showed that religiosity and traditional culture were negatively correlated to FLFP. In addition, age, marital status, number of children had a negative impact. In contrast, higher income levels and education influenced the FLFP positively. Thus, it has been established that religion, religiosity, and culture are strong determinants of FLFP. The enduring nature of these variables means that policymakers cannot influence them in the short to medium run only by policy alone. Hence, any policy designed to promote female participation in the workforce or gender equality must consider the underlying boundaries set by the existing religion and cultural values. Likewise, policymakers need to consider the underlying boundaries set by religion and culture in a country. Support to families with young children, particularly parental leaves and childcare subsidies, is also identified as raising female participation. Longer parental leaves and child benefits, on the other hand, could depress it. Other policies that impact positively on female participation are: avoiding regulations that impede the growth of service sectors; immigration policies (because they impact on the relative cost of child care); and welfare delivered through make-work-pays schemes. The policymakers should attempt to align their frameworks with these dominant influencers.

Reference

- Abazi, H., & Atanasovska, V. (2016). Female labour force participation: The case of Macedonia. *Journal of WEI Business and Economics-August*, 5(2).
- Abdelhadi, E. (2017). Religiosity and Muslim women's employment in the United States. *Socius*, 3, 2378023117729969.
- Abdelhadi, E. (2019). The Hijab and Muslim women's employment in the United States. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 61, 26-37.
- Alam, M., & Ansari, V. A. (2020). Are Islamic indices a viable investment avenue? An empirical study of Islamic and conventional indices in India. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*.
- Amin, S., Diamond, I., Naved, R. T., & Newby, M. (1998). Transition to adulthood of female garment-factory workers in Bangladesh. *Studies in family planning*, 185-200.
- Atasoy, B. S. (2017). Female labour force participation in Turkey: The role of traditionalism. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 29(4), 675-706.
- Besamusca, J., Tijdens, K., Keune, M., & Steinmetz, S. (2015). Working women worldwide. Age effects in female labor force participation in 117 countries. *World Development*, 74, 123-141.
- Clark, M. F. (1985). Hiding, hurting, healing: Restoration for today's woman.
- Diwan, I., & Vartanova, I. (2017). *The effect of patriarchal culture on women's labor force participation*. Paper presented at the Cairo, Egypt: Economic Research Forum (ERF) Working Paper.
- Dollar, D., & Gatti, R. (1999). *Gender inequality, income, and growth: are good times good for women?* (Vol. 1): Development Research Group, The World Bank Washington, DC.
- Fernández, R. (2013). Cultural change as learning: The evolution of female labor force participation over a century. *American Economic Review*, 103(1), 472-500.
- Fukuda-Parr, S., Heintz, J., & Seguino, S. (2013). Critical perspectives on financial and economic crises: Heterodox macroeconomics meets feminist economics. *Feminist Economics*, 19(3), 4-31.
- Glass, J., & Nath, L. E. (2006). Religious conservatism and women's market behavior following marriage and childbirth. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 68(3), 611-629.
- Gu, M., Tan, J. H. L., Amin, M., Mostafiz, M. I., & Yeoh, K. K. (2021). Revisiting the moderating role of culture between job characteristics and job satisfaction: a multilevel analysis of 33 countries. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*.
- H'madoun, M. (2010a). Religion and labor force participation of women.
- H'madoun, M. (2010b). *Religion and labor force participation of women*: University of Antwerp Antwerp, Belgium.
- Ho, J. J. (2011). The Effect of Culture on Female Labor Force Participation.
- Klingorova, K., & Havlíček, T. (2015). Religion and gender inequality: The status of women in the societies of world religions. *Moravian Geographical Reports*, 23(2), 2-11.
- Kortt, M. A., Dollery, B., & Grant, B. (2013). The relationship between religious affiliation and returns to human capital for women. *Economic Papers: A journal of applied economics and policy*, 32(3), 395-404.
- Kuiper, E., & Barker, D. K. (2006). Feminist economics and the World Bank. *History, theory and policy*.
- Kus, M. (2011). The Role of Religion in Determining Female Labor Force Participation Rates. In
- Lechman, E., & Kaur, H. (2015). Economic growth and female labor force participation—verifying the U-feminization hypothesis. New evidence for 162 countries over the period 1990-2012. *New evidence for*, 162, 1990-2012.
- Mahony, W. K. (1995). Bhakti Religion in North India: Community Identity and Political Action. *Pacific Affairs*, 68(4), 610.
- Maton, K. I., Dodgen, D., Sto. Domingo, M. R., & Larson, D. B. (2005). Religion as a meaning system: Policy implications for the new millennium. *Journal of Social Issues*, 61(4), 847-867.
- Nnoromele, C. H. (2017). The Effects of Religion and Patriarchal Norms on Female Labor Force Participation. *Duke University Durham*.
- O'Brien, J., & Abdelhadi, E. (2020). Re-examining Restructuring: Racialization, Religious Conservatism, and Political Leanings in Contemporary American Life. *Social Forces*, 99(2), 474-503.
- Pastore, F., & Tenaglia, S. (2013). Ora et non labora? A test of the impact of religion on female labor supply.
- Reimer, S. H. (1995). A look at cultural effects on religiosity: A comparison between the United States and Canada. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 445-457.
- Seguino, S. (2011). Help or hindrance? Religion's impact on gender inequality in attitudes and outcomes. *World Development*, 39(8), 1308-1321.
- Sharabi, M. (2011). Culture, religion, ethnicity and the meaning of work: Jews and Muslims in the Israeli context. *Culture and Religion*, 12(3), 219-235.
- Sharabi, M., Shdema, I., & Abboud-Armaly, O. (2020). Nonfinancial employment commitment among Muslims

- and Jews in Israel: examination of the core–periphery model on majority and minority groups. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*.
- Sinclair, K. (1986). Women and religion. *The cross-cultural study of women: A comprehensive guide*, 107-124.
- Spierings, N. (2014). How Islam influences women’s paid non-farm employment: Evidence from 26 Indonesian and 37 Nigerian provinces. *Review of Religious Research*, 56(3), 399-431.
- Spierings, N., & Smits, J. (2007). *Women’s labour market participation in Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, Syria & Tunisia: A three-level analysis*. Paper presented at the IZA-World Bank Conference on Employment and Development.
- Taj, S., & Sinclair, K. (2020). Role of authentic employer brands in addressing the integration-responsiveness problem in religiously-sensitive environments. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*.
- Tausch, A., & Heshmati, A. (2016). Islamism and gender relations in the Muslim world as reflected in recent World Values Survey data. *Society and Economy*, 38(4), 427-453.
- Tzannatos, Z. (1999). Women and labor market changes in the global economy: Growth helps, inequalities hurt and public policy matters. *World Development*, 27(3), 551-569.
- Uür, Z. B. (2018). The Wearing of the Headscarf & Labor Market Outcomes for Women in Turkey. *KADEM Kadın Arastirmaları Derg.*, 4, 51-75.
- Vega Arias, X. M. (2020). Religion, women’s role, and the educational gender gap in sub-Saharan Africa.
- Womick, J., Woody, B., & King, L. A. (2021). Religious Fundamentalism, Right-wing Authoritarianism, and Meaning in Life. *Journal of Personality*.
- Yonay, Y. P., Yaish, M., & Kraus, V. (2015). Religious heterogeneity and cultural diffusion: The impact of Christian neighbors on Muslim and Druze women’s participation in the labor force in Israel. *Sociology*, 49(4), 660-678.
- Zelekha, Y., Avnimelech, G., & Sharabi, E. (2014). Religious institutions and entrepreneurship. *Small business economics*, 42(4), 747-767.

Author Information

Fouzia Yasmin

University of Sahiwal, Pakistan
Lecturer, Department of Economics

Noreen Safdar

The Woman University Multan, Pakistan
Assistant Professor, Department of Economics

Fatima Ali

Lecturer department of history and Pakistan studies
The women university Multan.

Iqra Ashraf

Lecturer department of history and Pakistan studies
The women university Multan.
